

ABA-Inspired Robotic Behavior Management Using PDDL in Educational Settings

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Abstract—This study presents a robotic architecture for managing behavior in educational settings, drawing inspiration from Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA). We introduce a novel system built on the Planning Domain Definition Language (PDDL) framework, enabling real-time adaptability. The paper outlines ABA-based methods, application scenarios, system architecture, concluding with directions for future work.

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper introduces a novel robotic architecture for behavior management in educational settings, inspired by Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) [1]. Despite its controversial role in supporting individuals with neurodevelopmental disorders [2], we suggest that an ABA-inspired robot capable of reasoning about the purposes of others’ behaviors can be a useful support in educational settings.

Social robots are increasingly used in education as social mediators, often applying ABA techniques [3]. Research on behavior change in human-robot interaction (HRI) has shown that motivational strategies employed by robots can positively influence habit modification [4]. Additionally, studies have examined how Theory of Mind (ToM) – the ability to recognize others’ mental states [5] – can be implemented in robots, impacting trust and decision-making in HRI [6].

Robots in HRI still lack autonomy in recognizing and responding to the goals of other agents. To address this limitation, we present a new architectural system built on the Planning Domain Definition Language (PDDL) framework, enabling real-time adaptation and allowing robots to autonomously manage interactions.

II. BACKGROUND AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

ABA is an evidence-based approach aimed at improving socially significant behaviors [1]. Within the ABA framework, behavior is conceptualized as purposeful (functional) and is always influenced by stimuli occurring before (antecedents) and after it (consequences). Functional Behavior Assessment (FBA) [7] is the process of identifying the functions or purposes of behavior. This study considers two functions:

- *Gain a Tangible*: i.e. the purpose of behaviors aiming at obtaining preferred stimuli or items.

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- *Escape*: i.e. the purpose of behaviors aiming at avoiding unpleasant situations.

FBA also provides valuable support to educators by offering a structured method for managing complex behaviors in a classroom setting. Building on these concepts, the long-term goal of this work is to develop an autonomous social robot that can plan educational activities, monitor children’s behavior, conduct FBA to identify the purposes of challenging behaviors, and suggest strategies for addressing them. The objective is not to label behaviors, but to address a common classroom challenge: managing behaviors that disrupt the learning environment.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE FOR BEHAVIORAL CHANGE

We designed a software architecture integrating cloud-based processing with local execution capabilities to achieve effective and autonomous behavior management in CRI.

Fig. 1: System architecture for behavioral change.

Figure 1 illustrates the proposed system architecture, divided into two main components: the Server and the Client. The workflow begins with the Plan Manager sending the domain and the problem files, to the Planner Engine. The latter processes the inputs to generate an efficient plan, which is then returned to the Plan Manager. The Behaviour Manager receives the plan and begins iterating through it. When an action is ready for execution, the Behaviour Executor takes over. Throughout this process, the Behaviour Manager continuously monitors the predicates retrieved by the PDDL Predicate

Retriever, which employs OpenAI for dynamic information retrieval. By comparing these retrieved predicates with the predefined ones in the dictionary file, the Behavior Manager ensures the robot’s actions align with the plan and can adapt to real-time environmental changes.

Drawing from ABA and FBA principles, two behavior functions were identified for testing the model’s validity: *Gain a Tangible* and *Escape*. The aim is that, through verbal interaction with the child, the robot would be able of autonomously recognizing the occurrence of the following behaviors:

- *Gain a Tangible*: When pleasant activities are interrupted, negative reactions of the child may be elicited.
- *Escape*: When presented with a task, a child may perceive it as too difficult or too boring, potentially provoking adverse responses to avoid the task.

We developed a PDDL domain capable of autonomously managing various scenarios of interest. Leveraging actions detailed in Table I, the framework can adapt to different situations, including real-time adjustments. Notably, the PDDL domain may include additional actions not directly related to behavior management, such as moving the robot to different areas. Consider the following scenario, where the initial problem generates a plan aimed at proposing a task and monitoring its advancement (see Table I for actions explanation):

```
(Interact game kid memory)
(PresentTask game kid memory)
(Wait game kid memory)
(WarningCleanUp game kid memory)
(PutAway game kid memory)
(ConfirmAllGood game kid memory x1 x2)
(GoodJob game kid memory x1 x2)
```

During the plan execution the robot may detect a task related issue by querying students via OpenAI-supported verbal interactions. This detection updates the predicates describing the current state, prompting a replanning process that may generate a new sequence of actions, beginning with:

```
(DiscoverTOM1 game kid memory)
```

This action is intended to prompt further replanning, engaging in a conversation to better understand and confirm the child’s ToM. Alternative plans might include:

```
(ConfirmHardTask game kid memory x1 x2)
(StrategyHardTask game kid memory x1 x2)
(GoodJob game kid memory x1 x2)
```

This case confirms that the child believes the task is too hard and the robot will act accordingly to the *Escape* function.

Action	Description
DiscoverTOM	Prompt conversation to asses child’s ToM
GoodJob	Praise child for achievement
PresentTask	Explain task rules in detail
PutAway	Ensure the child stops playing
StrategyHardTask	Apply strategy if child finds task hard
StrategyWant2Play	Apply strategy if child still wants to play
Wait	Wait and monitor task execution
WarningCleanUp	Warn about time and monitor completion

TABLE I: PDDL Actions related to Behavior Management.

IV. WORKPLAN

In line with the framework described in Section III, we are currently running structured experiments. Adult participants, simulating children’s behavior, are involved to test the robot’s replanning capabilities in a controlled environment.

The following key metrics are being measured:

- *Replan Time and Frequency*: tracks the time it takes for the robot to complete a replan after a disruption, as well as how often replanning occurs.
- *Cloud Response Time*: measures the time required for the robot to communicate with cloud services, process the data, and receive a response.
- *Efficacy of Replan*: assesses how effectively the robot adapts its actions, identifies key predicates, and achieves its intended goals despite interruptions.

These experiments provide valuable data on the robot’s ability to handle real-time disruptions, which will inform future trials involving children.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a framework to enhance child-robot interaction through behavior analysis principles. The system architecture features an innovative approach capable of online replanning to adapt to user behavior. Initially, our model will not include the child’s levels of motivation and attention during tasks. These factors are crucial for accurately recognizing the child’s purpose of behavior in the proposed setting. Further research is necessary to integrate these aspects and refine the model.

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